

NO TIME TO WAIT 3

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*“Just using '**open stuff**' won't fix your problems.
It might even make things worse.”*

...which btw applies to **any** digital system/tool, if not incorporated or used properly.
Independent of its license.

Speaker notes

Addressing this, because of archivist's reply in Frankfurt: “We used OpenSource as free alternative for 'the real X', but it didn't work as well as 'the real X', so we gave up and bought 'the real X'.”

POPULAR "MISTAKES"

- Underestimating environmental- and starting conditions.
- Do you value "digital freedoms" or just looking for cheap?
- No continuous allocation of resources (time *or* money).
- No community involvement: "*I'm not a coder*".

Speaker notes

- Environmental / starting conditions:
- especially (tech-)knowhow, because: You either have to pay -or- DIY.
 - staff moral / willingness to "question mainstream".
 - Lack of interfaces with proprietary systems.
 - Unexpected vendor lock-in.
 - Proprietary file formats / dialects of open standards...

(YOUR) REASONS TO USE FOSS?

*“I need a **free** alternative for X, because we ain't got enough budget to get the **real** X.”*

*“Your stuff's for free, right?
Good, because we need the money to pay
proprietary vendor-lock-in system X.”*

*“We want to study/share/improve our
digital workflows. Do you know a FOSS
system we could use or build on?”*

DEFINE FREE/REAL?

Free X:

Gratis?

Cheap - as in "unprofessional" or less valuable/reliable/awesome?

Worth less than non-free (water...)?

Freedom to Use, Study, Share & Improve (USSI)?

Part of a digital commons infrastructure?

Real X:

The "Wow! you can afford that? I'm jealous." option?

The professional tool?

The number one that everyone uses?

The one with the great GUI?

The well-supported one?

Speaker notes

Different definitions of "free" change the outcome. Any software is as good as what the user "expects" it to be. Bad software + excellent PR/image = perceived as great software ;P And the other way around.

WHAT IF...

Real = Free?

- Any reason **not** to want that?
- How much would that be worth to you?
- Do you expect free to be as good as non-free (water)?

Speaker notes

Is this even possible? Well, if FOSS was the supported mainstream we'd be pretty close to that.

UNPOSSIBLE?!

Speaker notes

Compare it to: claiming a forest is a stable ecosystem - and possible - but noone ever saw a forest, and challenge you to prove it. By letting you plant a tree (from seed) on a heavy-traffic highway.

“Environmental- and starting conditions matter.”

Speaker notes

At least here the tree will survive. But will it become a self-sustaining forest?

“Shared, public code makes up the digital infrastructure of our society today.”

Speaker notes

Quote: "In the face of unprecedented demand, the costs of not supporting our digital infrastructure are numerous. No individual company or organization is incentivized to address the public good problem alone. In order to support our digital infrastructure, we must find ways to work together."

INFRASTRUCTURE? TAXES?

- Good: Most publicly funded projects now require FOSS license :)
- But: Public institutions sometimes not "allowed" to pay for FOSS :(
- Demand/help change of rules:
Public Money? Public Code! (publiccode.eu)

ABANDONED ORPHANS

“No developer likes to admit to have to give up, abandon his code work. It's quite emotional. Seriously.”

How to make sure projects we like, or rely on, stay alive and flourish?

TOP REASONS FOR FOSS DEVELOPERS TO LEAVE A PROJECT:

- lack of interest
- lack of patience
- lack of resources (time/money)
- change of profession
- creative differences

Speaker notes

These reasons actually apply to: "why someone quits a job". Therefore also to proprietary software, but you just don't see it that often from "outside", as it's company-internal dynamics. Providing means for developers to stay on, or adopt a project will not only avoid it becoming abandoned, but will improve its qualities: stability, features and GUI.

TAKEN FOR GRANTED?

- Who of you is using:
MediaInfo, VLC, Wikipedia, Firefox, FFmpeg, QCTools, Linux, etc...?
- What if they disappear? 🤖
- What's your (institution's) plan to keep these applications alive and kicking?

HOW MUCH DO YOU VALUE 'IT'?

Speaker notes

Difficult to judge the value of immaterial goods in our society... So what about real stuff? Let's try comparison with food and sustainable environment.

YOUR PREFERENCE?

1. Industrial, patented, lock-in seeds, exploit nature for profit (= **Proprietary**)
2. organic, sustainable, community, handmade (= **FOSS**)

- Which one's required for sustainable long-term?
- Which one's the current mainstream?
- Which profits whom?
- Which one has the shinier apples?

YOU *ARE* 'THE COMMUNITY'

CONTRIBUTIONS

- Value FOSS like fresh air or clean water.
- Offer your time or money.
- Write documentation.
- Publish tutorials.
- Design graphics.
- Testing.
- Raising funds.
- Demand FOSS and open file formats.
- ...

SUMMARY

- Environmental- and starting conditions matter.
- Encourage and value "digital freedoms".
- Contribute, if possible :)
- Allocate continuous resources (time *or* money)
- Think long-term & in collaborations.

- THE END -

QUESTIONS? COMMENTS?

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ABOUT MYSELF

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- Studied media computer-science at the TU Vienna
- Developer, trainer and tech-consultant since 2000
- 8 years working with broadcast audio archives around the globe ([NOA](#))
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